

lines that showed resistance in the first test were screened again. For the 9 that still showed resistance, insect preference and the number of eggs laid on leaves of

each rice line were recorded. Resistant Colombo and Rathu Heenati and susceptible TN1 were used as controls. Lines with high resistance scores had

fewer eggs and fewer insects than susceptible TN1. IR5853-198-1-Mr-3-2 had fewest eggs and insects. □

Reaction of rice varieties to gall midge in Tamil Nadu

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Gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) is a destructive pest of rice in Tamil Nadu, particularly Madurai, Tanjore, and Trichi districts. Sep infestations cause 25 to 30% yield loss.

From Aug to Dec 1981, 46 prerelease and released varieties from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad, were field-screened at Thaniamangalam, Madurai. Each variety was grown in a single 3-m-long row in 3 replications. GM infestation was encouraged by growing TN1 on borders, cutting tillers, keeping water in the plots to attract flies, and lighting plots at night. Total number of hills infested were recorded (see table). Six varieties were not infested (see table). □

Field screening of rice varieties for gall midge resistance, Madurai, Tamil Nadu, 1981.^a

Variety	Hills infested ^b (%)	Variety	Hills infested ^b (%)
IET6056	45.8 a	IET7329	16.4 bcdefghij
IR20	41.7 ab	Eswarakora	15.2 bcdefghij
Chitraikar	36.3 abc	W1263	14.1 bcdefghij
TN1	35.0 abcd	IET17327	14.0 bcdefghij
Vaigai	34.3 abcde	PTB10	13.3 cdefghij
Karuna	31.3 abcdef	IET6101	13.3 cdefghij
IET6579	31.0 abcdef	IET7012	12.5 cdefghij
Chandrikar	29.7 abcdefg	IET7236	9.1 cdefghij
IET7328	28.8 abcdefgh	IET7013	8.1 cdefghij
IET7174	28.8 abcdefgh	IET6109	6.9 efghij
IET6296	28.2 abcdefghi	IET6 266	6.6 efghij
Bhavani	26.5 abcdefghij	IET6 727	4.9 fghij
Jaya	25.8 abcdefghij	IET7014	4.6 fghij
IET6730	25.2 abcdefghij	IET6293	2.7 ghij
Puduvai Ponni	24.8 abcdefghij	IET6286	1.3 hij
IR8	23.6 abcdefghij	IET7015	0.6 ij
Kakatiya	23.1 abcdefghij	Vikram	0.6 ij
IET6080	22.1 abcdefghij	IET7010	0.0 j
PTB21	21.8 abcdefghij	Phalguna	0.0 j
MDU-1	19.7 abcdefghij	IET7016	0.0 j
Kuruvai	17.4 bcdefghij	IET6290	0.0 j
IET6757	17.1 bcdefghij	IET7009	0.0 j
IET7026	16.5 bcdefghij	IET7008	0.0 j
CV (%) = 81.27		F value = 2.56** at 1% level.	

^aAv of 3 replications. ^bMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 1% level.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Hybrid rice

Isolation of maintainers and restorers for Chinese male-sterile lines

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Following successful development of cytoplasmic genetic male-sterile lines in China, heterosis breeding of rice became a commercial reality. We sought to identify effective, stable restorers for the Chinese cytoplasmic genetic male-sterile lines Zhen Shan 97A, Er Jiu Nan 1A, and V20A. We evaluated many crosses, in-

Table 1. List of complete restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers identified at Delhi and Aduthurai, India, for Chinese cytoplasmic genetic male-sterile lines, 1982.

Male-sterile line	Complete restorers (R)	Partial restorers (PR)	Maintainers (M)
	<i>Delhi (kharif)</i>		
Zhen Shan 97A	Pusa 245-51-1 Pusa 212 IR26 IR36 IR9761-19-1 IR19793-25-2-2-2 IET4141 Mijingem	TKM6 ADT33 IR9782-111-2-1-2 Pak Bas 177 Gharbharan Ratna Saket 4	Pusa 3 12 Pusa 150-21-1 ITA225 ITA 119 ITA118 ITA 141 ITA117 ITA175 ITA116 AC5725 Bas 370 Type 3 Karnal Local

Continued on next page

cluding traditional tall and improved dwarf varieties and elite breeding lines at Delhi in kharif and at Aduthurai in kuruvai and summer. Percent spikelet fertility of F₁ hybrids was used as fertility index. Lines that restored 80% or more spikelet fertility were classified as complete restorers, those restoring between 79% and 10% were partial restorers, and those with less than 10% were called maintainers (see table).

Results of crosses of the three male-sterile lines with pollinators indicate that they have a similar cytoplasmic background. The study suggested that environment may influence the level of fertility restoration. For instance, ADT33, which was classified as a complete restorer to V20A during kuruvai at Aduthurai, was only a partial restorer to Zhen Shan 97A and V20A during kharif at Delhi. Similarly, NDC50, which was a complete restorer to V20A at Delhi, was a partial restorer to Er Jiu Nan 1A during summer at Aduthurai. However, most restorers or maintainers performed consistently. IR26, Pusa 37-3, and Pusa 245-51-1 were among the most effective and stable restorers and showed good hybrid vigor. □

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgment to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Table continued.

Male-sterile line	Complete restorers (R)	Partial restorers (PR)	Maintainers (M)
		<i>Delhi (kharif)</i>	
V20A	Pusa 518-1 Pusa 245-51-1 Pusa 37-3 Pusa 212 IR19793-25-2-2-2 IR50 IR9761-19-1 IR52 IR36 IR26 NDC28 NDC50 IET4141 Mijingem	Pusa 167-120-3-2 Pusa 293-42-1 Pusa 499-6-3 Pusa 152-1 Pusa 150-82-1-2-3 Pusa 371-2-8-2 IR9782-111-2-1-2 IR30 IR43 ADT33 BJ1 TKM6 Pak Bas 177 Gharbharan Ratna Saket 4	Pusa 147-2 Pusa 33-18-1 Pusa 312 ITA118 ITA141 ITA117 ITA175 ITA116 ITA225 ITA162 ITA183 UPRM500 PAU29 AC5725 Bas 370 Nagina 22 Type 3 Karnal Local Imp. Sabarmati BPi-Ri-6 CH1039 dwarf mutant
		<i>Aduthurai, 1982 summer</i>	
Zhen Shan 97A	Pusa 269 ADT35 ASD15 J141 ITA 164	IR13256 Kapoor Chini NDC88 PR106 Jaya	Culture 340 Pusa 312 PAU29 CH1039 dwarf mutant Peta
Er Jiu Nan 1A	UPI-Ri-3 Mijingem D241 C171-120 CR156-50-21-207 IET4141 Pusa 512-1 Pusa 269 Pusa 145 Pusa 5164-1 Pusa 29342-1 IR9671-19-1 IR5853-68 IR89974-4-2 IR26 IR36 IR50 IR52	Pusa 371-5-2 Pusa 150-82 ADT35 NDC50 Pak Bas 177 Gharbharan DGWG	Pusa 368-1 CH41 Co 33 TKM8 Seratus Malam MTU3419 ITA116 ITA225 ITA173 PAU29 BPi-Ri-6 IR32
V20A	IR50 ASD15 ADT35	Pusa 152-1	Pusa 312 CR1014 UPRM500
		<i>Aduthurai, 1982 kuruvai</i>	
Zhen Shan 97A	RSII Pusa 269 ASD11	IR20 Ponni Pusa 150 Pusa 506-1-1-1	CH1039 dwarf mutant
Er Jiu Nan 1A	UPI-Ri-3		IARI 10560 Seratus Malam Co 33 Bas 370
V20A	IR9828-91-2-3 Ponni ADT33 ASD15 Mahsuri Boothy	Pusa 150	